

THEOREM ABOUT THE DECENT FRACTION OF THE NUMBER OF TURNS IN CIRCULAR REFLECTIONS AS WELL AS ITS DENOMINATOR

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ТЕОРЕМА О ПРИЛИЧНОЙ ДРОБИ ЧИСЛА ВИТКОВ В КРУГОВЫХ ОТРАЖЕНИЯХ, А ТАКЖЕ О ЕЕ ЗНАМЕНАТЕЛЕ

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AYLANA AKSLANTIRISHLARIDA BURISH SONINING MUNOSIB KASRI HAMDA UNING MAXRAJI HAQIDA TEOREMA

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abstract

In this work, the deflection number ρ – is an irrational orientation-preserving T a circular homeomorphism is considered. T formulas for the denominator q_n of a decent fraction $\frac{p_n}{q_n}$ are found when the twisting numbers of a homeomorphism are $\rho^{(1)}(T) = \rho_f^{(1)} = [k_1, k_2, k_1, k_2, \dots, k_1, k_2, \dots]$, and

$\rho^{(2)}(T) = \rho_f^{(2)} = [k_2, k_1, k_2, k_1, \dots, k_2, k_1, \dots]$, $k_1, k_2 \in N$ bo'lganda $\frac{p_n}{q_n}$ munosib kasrning maxraji q_n

аннотация

В этом случае число витков ρ – это хранитель направления, которое иррационально T гомеоморфизм окружности рассматривается. Формула для знаменателя

q_n соответствующей дроби $\frac{p_n}{q_n}$ найдена при

T числах витков гомеоморфизма $\rho^{(1)}(T) = \rho_f^{(1)} = [k_1, k_2, k_1, k_2, \dots, k_1, k_2, \dots]$, и

$\rho^{(2)}(T) = \rho_f^{(2)} = [k_2, k_1, k_2, k_1, \dots, k_2, k_1, \dots]$, $k_1, k_2 \in N$

annotatsiya

Ushbu ishda burish soni ρ – irratsional bo'lgan yo'nalishni saqlovchi T aylana gomeomorfizmi qaralgan. T gomeomorfizmning burish sonlari $\rho^{(1)}(T) = \rho_f^{(1)} = [k_1, k_2, k_1, k_2, \dots, k_1, k_2, \dots]$, va

$\rho^{(2)}(T) = \rho_f^{(2)} = [k_2, k_1, k_2, k_1, \dots, k_2, k_1, \dots]$, $k_1, k_2 \in N$

uchun formulalar topilgan.

Keywords:

The number of turns, the orientation-preserving circle homeomorphisms, is a decent fraction.

Ключевые слова:

Число витков, гомеоморфизмы окружностей, сохраняющих ориентацию, приличная дробь.

Kalit so'zlar:

Burish soni, yo'nalishni saqlovchi aylana gomeomorfizmlari, munosib kasr.

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Main part

In dynamical system theory, the spread of real numbers over continuous fractions is important. An arbitrary $\rho \in (0,1)$ real number is spread out in the one-valued following representation ([1] - [3]):

$$\rho = \frac{1}{k_1 + \frac{1}{k_2 + \frac{1}{k_3 + \dots \frac{1}{k_n + \dots}}}} \quad (1)$$

Where $k_1, k_2, \dots, k_n, \dots$ - is the natural numbers. (1) the expression is called a continuous fraction, and it is defined in terms of $\rho = [k_1, k_2, \dots, k_n, \dots]$. Since the arbitrary real number a can be expressed in terms of $[a] + \{a\}$, it is sufficient to look at the case where $a \in [0,1)$. We take $\frac{p_n}{q_n} = [k_1, k_2, \dots, k_n]$, $n \geq 1$, and these are called decent fractions of the number ρ , where p_n and q_n satisfy the following recurrent relations for all $n \geq 1$:

$$p_{n+1} = k_{n+1}p_n + p_{n-1}, \quad p_0 = 0, p_1 = 1,$$

$$q_{n+1} = k_{n+1}q_n + q_{n-1}, \quad q_0 = 1, q_1 = a_1.$$

$\left\{ \frac{p_{2n-1}}{q_{2n-1}}, n \geq 1 \right\}$ the sequence grows monotonically, and $\left\{ \frac{p_{2n}}{q_{2n}}, n \geq 1 \right\}$ the sequence

decreases monotonically and approaches ρ .

We look at the direction preserving T Circle homeomorphism, where the number of turns is ρ - irrational. The spread of ρ to a continuous fraction: through $\rho = [k_1, k_2, \dots, k_n, \dots]$, $\frac{p_n}{q_n}$, we define the n - decent fraction of the number ρ . We take an optional $x_0 \in S^1$ and look at its trajectory.

$$O(x_0) = \{x_i = T^i x_0, i \geq 0\}$$

Points x_{q_n} and $x_{q_{n+1}}$ lie on different sides of the point. More precisely, if x_0 is odd n the point x_{q_n} lies on the left side of the point n is even, then x_0 lies on the right side of the point.([1]-[3])

Suppose T that the twisting numbers of a homeomorphism are

$$\rho^{(1)}(T) = \rho_f^{(1)} = [k_1, k_2, k_1, k_2, \dots, k_1, k_2, \dots], \quad \rho^{(2)}(T) = \rho_f^{(2)} = [k_2, k_1, k_2, k_1, \dots, k_2, k_1, \dots].$$

Theorem. The distribution of the $\rho_f^{(1)}$ and $\rho_f^{(2)}$ tilting numbers to the continuous fraction is seen as $\rho_f^{(1)} = [k_1, k_2, k_1, k_2, \dots, k_1, k_2, \dots]$ and $\rho_f^{(2)} = [k_2, k_1, k_2, k_1, \dots, k_2, k_1, \dots]$ respectively, and the relation is appropriate

$$q_n = \frac{k_1 \rho_1 + 1}{\rho_1^2 + 1} \rho_1^n + (-1)^n \frac{\rho_1^2 - k_1 \rho_1}{\rho_1^2 + 1} \rho_1^{-n}, \quad q_n = \frac{k_2 \rho_2 + 1}{\rho_2^2 + 1} \rho_2^n + (-1)^n \frac{\rho_2^2 - k_2 \rho_2}{\rho_2^2 + 1} \rho_2^{-n}, \quad n \geq 0$$

when $\frac{p_n}{q_n}$ is $\rho_f^{(1)} = [k_1, k_2, k_1, k_2, \dots, k_1, k_2, \dots]$ for the denominator of a decent fraction q_n , $q_0 = 1, q_1 = k_1, n \geq 1$ and $\rho_f^{(2)} = [k_2, k_1, k_2, k_1, \dots, k_2, k_1, \dots]$ in the initial conditions $q_0 = 1, q_1 = k_2, n \geq 1$.

Conclusion

We have given a theorem about the denominator of a decent fraction of the irrational number of turns, in which irrational turns occupy a very important place in numerical direction-preserving circle reflections.

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